

GOODS-ALMA 2.0: Understanding the role of compact star formation in galaxy evolution

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Massive elliptical galaxies in the local universe appear to have their high redshift analogs in the form of extremely compact quiescent galaxies. Therefore, it seems that compact star formation appears to play a pivotal role in the evolutionary pathways of massive galaxies across cosmic history. However, there are fundamental unresolved questions debated in the literature: How systematic is compact star formation in star-forming galaxies (SFGs) at high redshift? What is its role in the broader picture of the scaling relations in galaxy evolution? The results here presented shed light into these fundamental questions.

Compact star formation appears to be the norm in massive galaxies at high redshift and it unveils as a physical driver of the behaviour of massive galaxies in the scaling relations. Together, compact star formation appears to be fundamental in keeping galaxies as star forming systems even when their gas to fuel star formation is very low and they are presumably on their way to quiescence.

In this text the main results from Gómez-Guijarro [3, 4] are outlined, to which the reader is referred for further details.

ALMA 1.1 mm galaxy survey in GOODS-South

GOODS-ALMA is a 1.1 mm galaxy survey carried out with ALMA Band 6 in the GOODS-South field. It covers a continuous area of 72.42 arcmin^2 centered at $\alpha = 3^{\text{h}}32^{\text{m}}30^{\text{s}}$, $\delta = -27^{\circ}48'00''$ at a homogeneous sensitivity with two different array configurations, in order to include both small and large angular scales. The high resolution dataset was presented in Franco [2]. In this 2.0 version, we present the low resolution dataset and its combination with the high resolution dataset (combined dataset), reaching an average sensitivity of $\sigma = 68.4 \mu\text{Jy beam}^{-1}$ at an average angular resolution of $0.447'' \times 0.418''$. In Gómez-Guijarro [3], we construct a source catalog, derive number counts, and dust continuum sizes at 1.1 mm.

A total of 88 galaxies are detected in a blind search, compared to 35 in the high resolution dataset alone. We find 44 sources with a detection $S/N^{\text{peak}} \geq 5$ associated to a purity $p = 1$. Using a prior-based methodology we find another 44 sources with a detection $3.5 \leq S/N^{\text{peak}} < 5$. These galaxies span mostly $0.25 < S_{1.1\text{mm}} < 3 \text{ mJy}$, $1 < z < 4$, $\log(M_*/M_{\odot}) > 10$.

Among these galaxies, 13 out of the 88 are optically dark/faint sources, a new population of galaxies currently undetected or very faint in all optical and near-infrared bands up to and including the H -band (H -band dropouts) in the deepest cosmological fields ($H > 27 \text{ mag}$; 5σ point source), but bright at longer near-infrared bands ($[4.5] < 24 \text{ mag}$) [e.g., 10].

Prevailing compact dust continuum sizes

Dust continuum sizes at 1.1 mm are generally compact within the sample [see also e.g., 6, 5], with a median effective radius of $R_e = 0.10'' \pm 0.05''$ (physical size of $R_e = 0.73 \pm 0.29 \text{ kpc}$, at the redshift of each source). They are found to evolve with redshift and stellar mass resembling the trends of the stellar sizes measured at optical wavelengths, albeit a lower normalization compared to those of late-type galaxies [see 3, for details].

Figure 1: Physical dust continuum size at 1.1 mm scaled to the median redshift and stellar mass of the sample versus 1.1 mm flux density. The typical size of the stellar distribution measured at optical wavelengths for both early and late-type galaxies from van der Wel [9] are also shown. The grid of purple lines shows the region where the survey is no longer $\sim 100\%$ complete.

Compact dust continuum emission at 1.1 mm prevails for sources with flux densities $S_{1.1\text{mm}} > 1 \text{ mJy}$. Sizes as extended as typical star-forming stellar disks are rare (see Figure 1). At $S_{1.1\text{mm}} < 1 \text{ mJy}$, dust continuum emission at 1.1 mm appears slightly more extended, although they are still generally compact below the sizes of typical star-forming stellar disks. A larger scatter in the sizes in this flux regime is also seen, with some of the sources possibly entering the regime of the typical size of star-forming stellar disk, but the lower S/N and completeness associated to this flux regime would require further data to evaluate such sources (see Figure 1).

After covering a large contiguous area using two array configurations at a similar and homogeneous depth providing both small and large spatial scales, our findings indicate that dust continuum emission occurring in compact regions smaller than the stellar distribution appears to be a norm in dusty SFGs.

Compact star formation regulating galaxy evolution prequenching

In Gómez-Guijarro [4], we derive physical properties, such as star formation rates, gas fractions ($f_{\text{gas}} = M_{\text{gas}}/(M_{\text{gas}} + M_*)$), depletion timescales ($\tau_{\text{dep}} = M_{\text{gas}}/\text{SFR}$), and dust temperatures for the galaxy sample built from the survey and study them in the framework set by the scaling relations in galaxy evolution.

Figure 2: Top panel: Depletion timescale as a function of the distance to the main sequence of SFGs from Schreiber [7] with the scaling relation for $\tau_{\text{dep}}(z, M_*, \Delta_{\text{MS}})$ from Tacconi [8] in blue. Bottom panel: As star formation regions become more compact compared to the sizes of typical main sequence SFGs stellar disks at the same stellar mass and redshift (increasing X-axis), the gas fraction become lower compared to typical gas fraction of typical main sequence SFGs at the same stellar mass and redshift (decreasing Y-axis). Star formation regions shrink with decreasing gas content. Starburst in the main sequence are located at the extreme (highlighted in red) with the most compact star formation regions and the lowest gas content.

Our galaxy sample is located above and within the main sequence of SFGs [e.g., 7]: 42% above the main sequence ($\Delta_{\text{MS}} = \text{SFR}/\text{SFR}_{\text{MS}} > 3$) and 58% are in the main sequence within a factor 3 ($0.33 < \Delta_{\text{MS}} = \text{SFR}/\text{SFR}_{\text{MS}} < 3$, 0.5 dex).

There exist a subset of galaxies that exhibit short depletion timescales compared to typical SFGs at the same redshift, stellar mass, and distance to the main sequence. At the same time, these galaxies are located within the scatter of the main sequence. Therefore, we dubbed them as “starbursts in the main sequence” [see also 1] (see Figure 2, top panel). They also exhibit low gas fractions and high dust temperatures in comparison with typical main sequence SFGs at the same stellar mass and redshift. Besides, they account for $\sim 60\%$ of the most massive galaxies in the sample ($\log(M_*/M_{\odot}) > 11.0$).

We find that as galaxies become more compact compared to typical SFGs stellar disks, depletion timescales and gas fractions become lower, and dust temperatures higher, compared to typical main sequence SFGs, at the same stellar mass and redshift [see 4, for details]. These trends manifest a direct link between a geometrical property like the sizes of the ongoing star formation regions and other physical properties of the galaxies. Starbursts in the main sequence appear to be located at the extremes of the trends (see Figure 2, bottom panel).

Our findings suggest that the star formation rate is somehow sustained in very massive SFGs, keeping them within the main sequence even when their gas fractions are low and they are presumably on their way to quiescence. It seems that gas and star formation compression allows to hold their star formation rate.

References

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Short CV

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